

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART V

BY A. B. SEN AND S. S. PARMAR

Several *ortho*-chlorobenzyl and allyl ethers of *ortho*-acyl-*p*-bromophenol have been prepared with a view to testing their insecticidal activity.

The benzylaryl and allylaryl ethers of halophenols may be expected to be good contact insecticides, in view of the fact that they contain a neurotoxic haloaryl group and an ether linkage having lipophilic properties (T. C. Chen and Sumerford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4694). The introduction of the ketonic group, which would possibly increase their lipid solubility, may further enhance their insecticidal activity. Attempts have now been made to combine these insecticidally active groups in order to obtain additional and possibly improved insecticides. For this purpose two series of ethers, viz., *ortho*-chlorobenzylaryl and allylaryl ethers of *ortho*-acyl-*p*-bromophenols were prepared having one halogen atom in the benzene nucleus as *para* substituent. The *ortho*-hydroxyketones were prepared in the usual manner by the Fries rearrangement of the appropriate esters of *p*-bromophenol. These ketones were converted into *o*-chlorobenzyl and allyl ethers by refluxing a mixture of the appropriate *o*-hydroxyketone with an equivalent amount of *o*-chlorobenzyl chloride or allyl bromide and freshly fused potassium carbonate in acetone on a water-bath for 8 hours. The ketonic ethers, thus obtained, were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from hot glacial acetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The esters of *p*-bromophenol, viz., acetate, propionate, butyrate, valerate, caproate and heptoate were prepared in the usual manner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4657). The ester of heptylic acid was analysed. (Found : C, 54.31 ; H, 5.67. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2Br$ requires C, 54.74 ; H, 5.97 per cent).

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The rearrangement of the above esters was carried out in the usual manner. The *o*-hydroxyketone obtained from the ester of heptylic acid was analysed. (Found : C, 54.52 ; H, 5.57. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2Br$ requires C, 54.74 ; H, 5.57 per cent). This 5-bromo-2-hydroxyheptophenone was converted into its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone which was crystallised from hot glacial acetic acid, m. p. 189°. (Found : N, 11.68. $C_{19}H_{21}O_5N_4Br$ requires N, 12.04 per cent).

Preparation of o-Chlorobenzylaryl and Allylaryl Ethers.—A mixture of *o*-hydroxyketone (0.1 M), an equivalent quantity of *o*-chlorobenzyl chloride or allyl bromide, freshly fused potassium carbonate and acetone (100 c.c.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 8 hours. A heavy precipitate of potassium halide began to form soon after the refluxing was started. After cooling, water was added and the mixture was taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed with 10% NaOH solution. The ethereal layer was further washed with water and dried over freshly fused potassium carbonate, the ether removed and the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure. The *o*-chlorobenzylaryl and allylaryl ethers were thus obtained in yields ranging from 54.5 to 83.5% (Tables I and II). These ethers were characterised through their 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

TABLE I

o-Hydroxy-ketones.	B.P.	o-Chlorobenzyl ether Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Mol. formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
R-acetophenone	119°/6 mm.	54.5%	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	52.87	53.02	3.13	3.33	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	252°	10.35	10.78
R-propiophenone	107°/5	77.7	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	53.96	54.32	3.67	3.94	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	173°	10.03	10.50
R-butyrophenone	152°/6	79.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	55.03	55.51	3.89	4.35	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	184°	9.78	10.23
R-valerophenone	157°/6	80.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	56.13	56.62	4.31	4.72	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	193°	9.61	9.97
R-caprophenone	209°/6	71.3	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	57.22	57.65	4.76	5.06	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	163°	9.25	9.73
R-heptophenone	138°/5	83.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ ClBr	58.39	58.61	4.92	5.37	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	129°	9.01	9.50

R = 5-bromo-2-hydroxy.

TABLE II

o-Hydroxy-ketones.	M.P. or B.P.	Allyl ether Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Mol. formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
R-acetophenone	58°	62.4%	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	51.35	51.76	4.02	4.31	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	147°	12.38	12.87
R-propiophenone	64°	59.6	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	53.18	53.53	4.35	4.83	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	132°	12.06	12.47
R-butyrophenone	69°	58.4	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	54.89	55.12	4.92	5.30	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	148°	11.92	12.10
R-valerophenone	210°/6 mm.	61.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	56.14	56.57	5.57	5.72	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	188°	11.36	11.74
R-caprophenone	230°/6	62.7	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	57.52	57.88	5.91	6.11	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	146°	10.98	11.41
R-heptophenone	239°/6	79.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	58.76	59.08	6.03	6.46	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Br	152°	10.76	11.09

R = 5-bromo-2-hydroxy.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received May 31, 1953.